

GEOLOGICAL PROCESSES

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Abstract: *Geological factors mean the movement of the magma mass separated from the inner spheres of the earth in the lithospheric layers.*

Key words: *Geological factors, Hydrogeological factors, Atmospheric factors, Exogenous, Lithosphere, tectonic movements, Geosyncline areas.*

Introduction: It is known that geological processes are the natural processes that change the composition, structure, and condition of the earth's crust, as well as the formation of rocks.

Geological processes differ according to the duration of their occurrence: some of them are completed very quickly (volcanic eruptions, earthquakes), and some of them last for a very long time, continuously, quietly, for several million years (tectonic movements, the flow of rivers) and changes the external appearance and internal structure of the earth.

Exogenous geological processes take place on the earth's surface, and as a result of changes in temperature during the day and season, the influence of rain, storm water, the rise and fall of sea water, and the influence of wind, rocks are broken up and these pieces of broken rock are transported to different distances, is deposited and forms new sedimentary rock piles. Exogenous geological processes also include processes of sedimentary rock formation from skeletal remains of organisms and plant remains.

Endogenous geological processes mean the movement of the magma mass separated from the inner spheres of the earth in the lithospheric layers.

The main part: As a result of the folding or breaking of the rock layers, some parts of the earth's crust are raised along the surface of the cracks and as a result of the bending, it also includes the formation of mountain ridges and botiks. A part of this mass can leak to the surface of the earth through large cracks in the earth's crust.

During the movement of the magma mass along the lithospheric cracks, some parts of the lithosphere are strongly heated, the surrounding rocks are affected by solutions, gases, vapors with great pressure, and as a result, the composition, structure and state of the rocks change.

The interaction, interaction and unity of internal and external forces is the dialectic of the historical development of our planet.

Endogenous geological processes Endogenous geological processes include:

1. magmatism,
2. movement of the earth's crust
3. includes seismic events.

If the thermodynamic equilibrium is broken at the boundary between the lithosphere and the mantle (the temperature increases or the pressure decreases), the dense substances are absorbed into the liquid state. As a result of liquefaction, the density of substances decreases sharply, and their volume increases to a large extent. As a result, the conditions are created for the absorption of these dissolved liquid substances into the lithosphere and the differentiation of liquid substances begins. The sedimentary layers located above such parts of the earth's crust begin to sink, as a result, the rocks break and form large cracks, and liquid substances begin to flow out of these cracks to the surface of the earth.

Magmatism Processes associated with the penetration of liquefied substances into the lithosphere or flow to the surface of the earth, which appear under the influence of the Earth's internal forces, are called magmatism.

Tectonic movements are divided into interrelated types:

1. Oscillation movements manifested by the gradual rise of some parts of the earth's crust and the fall of other parts, or the horizontal displacement of these parts;

2. Fold-forming movements that lead to folding of rock layers into folds;

3. Movements that lead to the breaking of rock layers cause earthquakes and cause a strong shaking of the earth's crust, and in some places, rock rocks move away and crack.

The part of the Earth's crust characterized by weak and small-amplitude tectonic movements is called its platform, and the part characterized by strong and rapidly changing, large-amplitude movements is called a geosyncline. Vibrational tectonic movements.

No part of the earth is in a state of peace. Oscillations manifest themselves in the quiet, uneven vertical rise of some parts of the earth's crust and the subsidence of the surrounding parts.

The directions of movement are constantly changing, and previously expected areas may decrease.

Accordingly, it can be said that the vibrational movements are a constantly changing, irreversible fox-like process, the rise and fall does not occur in one part of the earth's crust at the same time, and every time the fox changes its position on the horizontal surface in space.

If the land subsides, the sea ash, the borders of the basins will change, the dry lands and the river valleys may be flooded.

If the lands with river valleys are protected, new terraces will be formed, their number and height will increase, their width will be small, and in the subsided lands, the number of river terraces will not exceed one, their height will be small, and the thickness of alluvial beds will be large.

Disruption of the primary state of the layers is called dislocations and occurs under the influence of endogenous and exogenous forces.

Laying of rocks in the form of folds. In a small part of the geosyncline regions, the phenomenon of folding occurs as a result of compression of rock

layers along the horizontal surface. Synclinal refers to folds with the concave side facing downwards, where the layers lie in one direction, and where the youngest rocks are located. The sides of the folds are called its wings. Discontinuous beds of rocks (discontinuous faults). As a result of tectonic processes, such a great stress is generated that the deformation ability of the rocks is reduced and a break appears in the layers.

Layers change their location as a result of breaks and fractures. The simplest appearance of fractures is widely distributed cracks in the earth's crust. According to their formation (genesis), cracks are divided into tectonic and non-tectonic cracks. Non-tectonic cracks include cracks formed in the process of rock formation, cracks resulting from the processes of folding, deformation, overturning, and thrusting. Tectonic faults are usually oriented in one direction or in several directions.

These cracks not only cut through layers of the same rock, but also cut through large rock layers of different ages and composition, dividing them into some blocks. Discontinuous faults can change the direction of the vertical and horizontal surfaces.

Displaced discontinuous faults take the form of sbros, vzbros (or aksbros), thrusts, horsts, and grabens. If the vertical wings move down along the sliding surface in a vertical or vertical direction, such a break is called sbros.

If the horizontal wing is placed in relation to the vertical wing, it is called an aft wing or vzbros. Grabens - refers to the dry part of the earth bounded by two sbros systems.

The part of the earth covered by the axis system is called horst.

Laying of rocks in the form of folds. In a small part of the geocyclinal regions, the phenomenon of folding occurs as a result of compression of rock layers along the horizontal surface. Synclinal refers to folds with the concave side facing downwards, where the layers lie in one direction, and where the youngest rocks are located.

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Discontinuous beds of rocks (discontinuous faults). As a result of tectonic processes, such a great stress is generated that the deformation ability of the rocks is reduced and a break appears in the layers. Layers change their location as a result of breaks and fractures. The simplest form of fractures are wide-spread cracks in the earth's crust. According to their formation (genesis), cracks are divided into tectonic and non-tectonic cracks.

Conclusion: Emergency situations related to geological processes, which we have studied above, are characterized by material damage and a large number of victims. However, it is possible to reduce the amount of damage from them. One of the ways to achieve this is to learn the causes, indicators and signs of their origin, to act correctly when the danger of these emergency situations appears and when they occur, calmly and rationally assessing the situation.

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